

First occurrence of Franklin's Gull (*Leucophaeus pipixcan*, Wagler 1831) in Ilha Comprida beach, Southern coast of São Paulo state, Brazil

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Abstract: Many seabirds of the Northern hemisphere migrate to South America in the non-breeding season, using several key stopovers and wintering sites along the Atlantic coast. Franklin's Gull *Leucophaeus pipixcan* breeds in central provinces of Canada and adjacent states of the northern United States. It is a migratory bird from the northern region of North America that flies southwards. However, there is little information about Franklin's Gull occurrence along the coast of the state of São Paulo. Former publications concerning the birds of Iguape-Cananeia-Ilha Comprida estuary did not mention the presence of this bird in the region. The two birds of this species were seen in September (2015), resting on the beach at Ilha Comprida. This note reports the first occurrence of Franklin's Gull in Ilha Comprida, Southern coast of São Paulo state, Brazil.

Keywords: Seabird, Migration, record, vagrant.

Resumo: Primeira ocorrência da gaivota-de-franklin (*Leucophaeus pipixcan*, Wagler 1831) na Ilha Comprida, Litoral sul de São Paulo, Brasil. Muitas aves marinhas do hemisfério Norte migram para as regiões de internada na América do Sul utilizando várias rotas e pontos de paradas ao longo da costa do Oceano Atlântico. A gaivota-de-franklin *Leucophaeus pipixcan* é uma ave marinha com ocorrência no interior dos Estados Unidos, e migra após a reprodução em direção a América do Sul. Entretanto, há poucas informações sobre a ocorrência de gaivota-de-franklin ao longo da costa do Estado de São Paulo. Publicações anteriores a respeito da avifauna do estuário de Iguape, Cananéia, Ilha Comprida não fazem menção à presença da gaivota-de-franklin na área. Dentro deste contexto, faz-se importante descrever essa ocorrência para o Estado de São Paulo, uma vez que há apenas um registro para a espécie nesse estado. Dois exemplares de gaivota-de-franklin foram observados e fotografados em duas oportunidades no mês de setembro de 2015, pousadas na praia da Ilha Comprida. Esta nota registra a primeira ocorrência de gaivota-de-franklin na Ilha Comprida, litoral sul do Estado de São Paulo, Brasil.

Palavras-chave: Ave Marinha, Migração, registro, vagante

Franklin's Gull (*Leucophaeus pipixcan*) is a small, monotypic gull (Smith, 2002) of the Laridae family and order Charadriiformes, migratory, spending the winter in areas along de West coast of

South America (Howell & Dunn, 2007). The body of adult birds, in summer, is white and the wings are dark gray, much darker than all other similar sized gulls, except for Laughing gull *Leucophaeus*

atricilla (Harrison, 1985). The wings have black tips with an adjacent white band. The tip of the beak and part of the legs are red. Adults have a black hood during the breeding season, which is practically inconspicuous in non-breeding season. Young individuals are similar to adults, but have less developed hood and lack the white band on the wings. Franklin's Gull takes three years to reach maturity. Omnivorous like most gulls (Smith 2002), this species search for small prey and dead fish on the beach. This bird species breeds in colonies near prairie lakes and build nests on the ground, or sometimes, floating nests (Howell & Dunn 2007). Females lay two to three eggs, like most gulls, which are incubated for about three weeks by both parents that take turns in incubating.

Franklin's Gull occurs in North America, where it breeds, and migrates during the winter to South America, staying on the coast of Peru, Chile, Patagonia and Tierra del Fuego (Argentina), Tristan da Cunha. Vagrants have been found in Europe, Africa, Kazakhstan, United Arab Emirates, Israel, China, Japan and Australia (Harrison 1985, Burger & Gochfeld 1996, Enticott & Tipling 1997, Olsen & Larsson 2003, Howell & Dunn, 2007, Dias *et al.* 2010, Wassink *et al.* 2011). In Brazil, there are records of the species in Fernando de Noronha (Antas *et al.*, 1988), Amazonas (Pacheco, 1995), in São Paulo coast (Almeida, 2003), in Rio Grande do Sul (Dias *et al.* 2010) Alagoas (Leal *et al.* 2013), Mato Grosso (Kantek & Onuma 2103), Maranhão (Gonsioroski 2014) This report aims to describe the first record of Franklin's Gull in Ilha Comprida, southern coast of São Paulo state, Brazil. Observation of Franklin's Gull were performed during bird censuses of the project "Birds of Ilha Comprida", developed along the beach of Ilha Comprida municipality, southern coast of São Paulo state, Brazil (Fig. 1).

The censuses began in the morning (8:30 AM), and were between 2 hours 30 minutes and 4 hours in duration. The Ilha Comprida beach was surveyed by car (medium speed = 40km/h) along the stretch of 70 km of beach and 0.2 km wide as used by Barbieri *et al.* (2013) in the Ilha Comprida Beach for study Charadriiformes, also proposed by Bibby *et al.*, (1992) to this kind of environment. The surveys were conducted from south to north (from Boqueirão Sul - Cananeia, to Canal de Icapara - Iguape (Fig. 1). Observations were made with 7 x 50 mm and 20 x 60 mm binoculars.

Two individuals of Franklin's Gull *Leucophaeus pipixcan* with non-breeding plumage

(Harrison 1985, Howell & Dunn 2007) were photographed at Ilha Comprida beach, on September 16th, 2015. One of the individuals was observed lonely on the beach at 24°54'55.30``S and 47°46'38.96``W nearby Pedrinhas neighborhood (Figure 2). The second individual was observed at 24°40'27.35`` S and 47°25'36.39``W in the Icapara channel, extreme north of the island, in a mixed-species flock with the Cabot's Tern *Thalasseus acuflavidus* and Royal Tern *T. maximus* (Figure 3).

Figure 1 – Area of occurrence of Franklin's Gull at Ilha Comprida, southern São Paulo, Brazil.

In South America, this gull is very common in sandy beaches, river mouths and farmed fields along the coast of Ecuador, central Chile and the Andean lakes, especially in Argentina (Burger & Gochfeld 1996). In Ilha Comprida, one specimen was observed resting on the sandy beach and the other interacting with fishing of Broadband anchovy *Anchoviella lepidentostole* on the north of the island. According to Dias *et al.* (2010), vagrant individuals in the Brazilian coast may come from the east of the Andes, which cross the mountain range and enter the continent through the Caribbean during their migration to the south. Tostain & Durjardin (1989) raise the hypothesis that this gull species is establishing new wintering areas in South America, based on several records of this species in Guiana Francesa.

In Brazil there are several record for the species in different regions (Table I). These, together with this event extends the importance of the publication, it addresses all records, plumage aspects, individuals registered, period of the year with more records and habitats of these records.

According to Sick (1997), the species is recorded as vagrant and rare, and using the same

Figure 2 - Franklin's Gull on the beach near the Pedrinhas neighborhood at Ilha Comprida southern São Paulo coast, Brazil.

Figure 3 – Franklin's Gull (behind) with other two seabirds the Royal Tern *Thalasseus maximus* and the Cabot's Tern *T. acutirostris* at the north of Ilha Comprida near the Icapara channel.

criteria, we can consider it as such for the state of São Paulo and the Southeastern region of Brazil, given the few records of its occurrence. Almeida (2003) recorded a single specimen on the coast of the state of São Paulo at coordinates 25°18'S, 45°16'W, a site very far from the mainland. Bird censuses conducted in Ilha Comprida by Barbieri & Paes (2008), Barbieri & Mendonça (2008), Barbieri

et al. (2010) and Numao & Barbieri (2011) have failed to record Franklin's Gull *L. pipixcan*, in this way, this is an important record for the state of São Paulo and the Southeastern region, by recording two specimens on the beach of the island in a single day.

This work presents the first record of *Leucophaeus pipixcan* on São Paulo state beach, for the first record for the species was recorded in the

ocean the same state.

Table I. All records in Brazil with the aspects of plumage, individuals registered, period of the year with more records, habitats of these records.

Local	Habitat	Data	Nº aves	Plumage	Estado	Referência
Aeroporto F. Noronha	ilha	16 May 1988	1	Not informed	Pernambuco	Antas <i>et al.</i> 1988
Rio Japurá	river	15 March 1994	1	Non-breeding	Amazonas	Pacheco 1995
Sul de São Paulo	ocean	7 Sept 2002	1	second-winter plumage	São Paulo	Almeida 2003
Foz da Lagoa dos Patos	beach	6 April 1999	1	Alternate plumage	Rio Grande do Sul	Dias <i>et al.</i> 2010
Praia dos Andradas – Trindade Island	beach	25 March 2007	1	Alternate plumage	Espírito Santo	Dias <i>et al.</i> 2010
Praia do Cassino	beach	11 January 2009	1	Non-breeding	Rio Grande do Sul	Dias <i>et al.</i> 2010
Praia do Cassino	beach	26 April 2009	1	Non-breeding	Rio Grande do Sul	Dias <i>et al.</i> 2010; WikiAves 2009
Praia de Cidreira	beach	30 May 2010	1	Alternate plumage	Rio Grande do Sul	Dias <i>et al.</i> 2010
Praia de Jacarecica	beach	27 July 2010	1	Not informed	Alagoas	Leal <i>et al.</i> 2013
Praia de Jacarecica	beach	8 May 2011	1	Breeding	Alagoas	Leal <i>et al.</i> 2013; WikiAves 2011
Pantanal – Rio Paraguai	river	21 May 2012	1	Breeding	Mato Grosso	Kantek & Onuma 2013
Ilha de Curupu	beach	10 Sept 2013	1	Non-breeding	Maranhão	Gonsioroski 2014; WikiAves 2013
Rio Juruá - Guarujá	beach	15 June 2013	1	Breeding	Amazonas	WikiAves 2013
Santo Amaro	beach	30 August 2015	1	Non-breeding	Bahia	WikiAves 2015
Saubara	beach	06 Sept 2015	1	Non-breeding	Bahia	WikiAves 2015
Ilha da Trindade	beach	11 May 2013	1	Breeding	Espírito Santo	WikiAves 2013
Quissamã	beach	15 Sept 2010	2	Non-breeding	Rio de Janeiro	WikiAves 2010
Rio de Janeiro	beach	19 April 2010	1	Non-breeding	Rio de Janeiro	WikiAves 2010
Forte dos Andradas - Guarujá	beach	02 Dec 2015	1	Non-breeding	São Paulo	WikiAves 2015
Peruíbe	beach	08 June 2013	1	Breeding	São Paulo	WikiAves 2013
Florianópolis	beach	03 March 2014	1	Non-breeding	Santa Catarina	WikiAves 2014
Praia de Cidreira	beach	08 Dec 2012	1	Non-breeding	Rio Grande do Sul	WikiAves 2012

Table I: Continued.

Local	Habitat	Data	Nº aves	Plumage	Estado	Referência
Lagoa do Peixe - Tavares	lagoon	30 March 2014	1	Non-breeding	Rio Grande do Sul	WikiAves 2014
Praia de Tramandai	beach	02 April 2015	1	Non-breeding	Rio Grande do Sul	WikiAves 2015
Praia de Tramandai	beach	02 May 2015	1	Breeding	Rio Grande do Sul	WikiAves 2012
Ilha Comprida	beach	16 Sept 2015	2	Non-breeding	São Paulo	Present study

It also contributes to the highlight of the Iha Comprida as a place of importance to stop to rest and feed coastal and marine birds nearctic during the wintering period in South America.

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